

POSSIBILITIES OF USING INTERACTIVE TOOLS IN EDUCATION

¹Nematov Bahron, ²Sharipov Abdumalik Ahmadovich, ³Ochilov Shakir Bakhtiyorovich,
⁴Mavlonova Yulduz Ilhomovna

^{1,3}Associate Professors of the Department of “Technological Education” of Navoi State
Pedagogical Institute

^{2,4}Teachers of the “Technological Education” department of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract. *The introduction of effective mechanisms for managing the educational system is the most important condition for raising the moral, moral and intellectual development of the young generation to a qualitatively new level, and also helps to use innovative forms and methods of education in the educational process. The article discusses different possibilities of using interactive tools in education.*

Keywords: *pedagogical, interactive, education, possibilities, technology, tools.*

The main basis of pedagogical technology in education is the teacher-trainer and the student - it depends on the selected technologies for the cooperation of students to achieve a guaranteed result from the set goal.

In the development of the higher education system, a number of strategic issues defined by our President include, mainly, the modernization of the education sector, increasing the quality of training highly qualified personnel for socio-economically stable development, training highly qualified personnel who can think creatively and make independent decisions based on international standards. , a number of urgent tasks have been defined, such as creating conditions for them to demonstrate their intellectual abilities and form them as spiritually mature individuals.

The introduction of effective mechanisms for managing the educational system is the most important condition for raising the moral, moral and intellectual development of the young generation to a qualitatively new level, and also helps to use innovative forms and methods of education in the educational process.

Legal, organizational, spiritual, pedagogical conditions for personnel training, formation of the culture of the individual during the development of the educational system, adaptation to life in society, knowingly choosing and then mastering professional and educational programs, educating a full-fledged person who understands his responsibilities to society, state, and family. aimed at providing conditions.

Interactive Tools - What is an interactive method? In traditional education, “what? when? and where?” problems, modern cooperative educational technologies focus on "How to teach?" the problem occupies an important place and is reflected in today’s education.

A teacher’s ability to behave in front of students, to be able to understand the student's situation, aspirations, interests and to find the most effective way is a pedagogical tactic.

Using rudeness, injustice, intimidation, insults, disdain, use of punitive methods contrary to pedagogy and other rude words that negatively affect their personality in communication with listeners can irreparably injure the hearts of listeners or damage the teacher's reputation.

The ratio of the contribution of teachers and students in the educational process was different in different periods of human development. At one time the educators were the leaders,

in certain periods the learners were the initiators and the positive and negative aspects of such activities have been researched. In the following decades, educational technologies based on the cooperative activity of the teacher and the learner are rapidly developing and becoming popular. Educators call such educational technologies “collaborative pedagogy”. Educational technologies based on such cooperation are widely used in developed countries such as the USA, Japan, Great Britain, and Germany, and high efficiency is being achieved. One of such educational technologies is based on interactive teaching methods. The word “inter” comes from Latin and means “intermediate”, “middle”, “between” in Uzbek. Therefore, interactive educational technologies are cooperation based on mutual activity between the teacher and the learner. Naturally, interactive educational technologies consist of interactive methods (methods) in the educational system.

It is based on cooperation, designed to increase the activity of students, students to hear, understand, respect the opinions of others, consider the interests of others, learn from them, teach them, be able to influence, perceive, feel, feel the “I” of yourself and others, feel yourself. “Interactive” teaching methods aimed at teaching to manage, to express one's thoughts clearly and clearly are developing rapidly and have a positive effect. Interactive methods create an atmosphere of competition between small groups in the group, encourage students to be active, and as a result, students learn to cooperate. Any interactive method, when used correctly and appropriately, will teach learners to think independently.

The use of problematic, real-life situations in interactive methods gives very good results. A controversial, problematic situation is when a person falls into a complex situation or situation, which depends on the result of thinking during his activity. In this case, he does not know how to interpret the event or process. Controversial and problematic situations strain the mental strength of students, they start looking for ways to clarify the situation, they encounter difficulties. A person begins to think only when faced with a problem. He begins to think and perform actions with the knowledge he has and comes to conclusions appropriate to his level.

Students should be able to tell and explain the assignments they have completed. They should be able to talk about what they think. It is very important for the teacher to be able to express in his own words the places he did not understand in the process of solving the problem.

Methods that teach students to actively work with information are called interactive methods.

Forms of Verbal Communication - Any high-level lecture, even if it is rich in facts, if it goes on for too long, the hearing ability of the students is weakened and tired. Therefore, the lectures organized on the basis of new pedagogical technology are effective.

The speaker divides his speech into several blocks. Each block lasts 15-20 minutes, and after each block there is a question-and-answer session.

During the lecture, he reveals some problems. During this period, he determines the attitude of students to this problem and listens to their opinions. Gives an opportunity to every commenter. His opinion is carefully listened to. But without criticizing him, other people's opinions are listened to. This situation changes the attitude towards the lecture in a positive direction, causes not to look at the lecture indifferently. Interviewing students lasts 5 minutes.

The lecturer monitors the growth of students' interest, aspirations, and responsibility. He continues the lecture and the same situation is repeated. During this period, active participants and those who express deep opinions become the speaker's support

During the lecture, the subject is gradually connected to the student's daily activities, and answers are gradually found based on short discussions.

In this case, in late lectures, students will not know how time has passed. Wanting the lecture to continue, indifference is replaced by vigilance, inner aspiration, search for a solution, and they themselves strive to contribute to finding a solution personally.

Such exposures increase mutual activity on both sides. Invites further discussions. While participating in such a lecture, the students want to see the rest of the lectures and when they will meet their teacher again.

Non-verbal means - Non-verbal means are to express or emphasize a meaning through facial expressions, hand and body movements. Nonverbal cues are extremely important and cannot be replaced. Every action of a person has a certain meaning, and these actions are understood differently in different nations. It is accepted to call these actions non-verbal speech. It is appropriate to mention that non-verbal speech consists of certain muscle movements of a person, including his thinking. It's no secret that a gesture is more powerful than words.

Visual tools - Visual tools include all tools designed for students to see with their eyes in the process of pedagogical technology. These include writing and other images on the blackboard, writing and images in books, handouts, educational posters, photographs, visual art works, video, film images, slides, handouts, animals, plants, natural objects, miscellaneous items, etc.

The use of visual aids in pedagogical technology gives students the opportunity to quickly, accurately and correctly explain the content related to the information to be taught in various forms and methods.

Audio tools - Audio tools provide an opportunity to learn and absorb information through hearing.

Nowadays, more and more audiovisual media are used, that is, media that serve to hear and see at the same time: movies and other sound video images.

In fact, based on the existing conditions and situations in practice, the best result can be the comprehensive use of existing tools based on a creative approach.

Natural tools - Natural means include all natural objects related to the content intended for learning in the process of pedagogical technology. These consist of people and animals, plants and nature, equipment, objects, machines, mechanisms, structures and so on.

Educational materials and school equipment necessary for students and teachers are necessary tools of pedagogical technology.

In conclusion, it should be said that the quality and effectiveness of pedagogical technology in general today largely depends on the quality of all kinds of necessary tools and the ability to use them with high efficiency.

In modern education, the realization of the goal and the achievement of a guaranteed result depend on the cooperative activity of both the teacher and the student, as well as the goal they set, the chosen method, form, tool, i.e. technology.

It is up to the teacher and the student-student to choose the technology to achieve the goal, because the main goal of both parties is to achieve a specific result, in which the teacher chooses the technology to be used depending on the level of knowledge of the student-students, the character of the group, and the conditions.

Correct and effective use of these tools depends on the teacher's skills, creativity, and curiosity.

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